

1 **Lef1 activation in solid tumors.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Citations

7 1. Giese, K. and Grosschedl, R., 1993. LEF-1 contains an activation domain that stimulates
8 transcription only in a specific context of factor-binding sites. *The EMBO journal*, 12(12), pp.4667-4676.

9 2. Tutter, A.V., Fryer, C.J. and Jones, K.A., 2001. Chromatin-specific regulation of LEF-1-β-catenin
10 transcription activation and inhibition in vitro. *Genes & development*, 15(24), pp.3342-3354.

11 3. Taniue, K., Kurimoto, A., Takeda, Y., Nagashima, T., Okada-Hatakeyama, M., Katou, Y., Shirahige,
12 K. and Akiyama, T., 2016. ASBEL–TCF3 complex is required for the tumorigenicity of colorectal cancer
13 cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(45), pp.12739-12744.

14 4. Gutierrez, A., Sanda, T., Ma, W., Zhang, J., Grebliunaite, R., Dahlberg, S., Neuberg, D.,
15 Protopopov, A., Winter, S.S., Larson, R.S. and Borowitz, M.J., 2010. Inactivation of LEF1 in T-cell acute
16 lymphoblastic leukemia. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*, 115(14),
17 pp.2845-2851.

18 5. Vadlamudi, U., Espinoza, H.M., Ganga, M., Martin, D.M., Liu, X., Engelhardt, J.F. and Amendt,
19 B.A., 2005. PITX2, β-catenin and LEF-1 interact to synergistically regulate the LEF-1 promoter. *Journal of
20 cell science*, 118(6), pp.1129-1137.